

Semi-rigorous propagation of astrometric parameters and their covariance

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1. Introduction

The propagation in time of stellar positions is normally based on the assumption of uniform space motion with respect to the solar system barycentre. This implies that the perspective changes of the proper motions are taken into account, which is rigorously possible if the full space velocity vector is known, including the radial velocity.

The propagation formula used by NDAC is given in A&A 258, 18 (1992), Eq. (A.1), and in ESA SP-1111, Vol. III, p. 173, Eq. [9.3]. (See also Eq. 21 below.) It includes the perspective acceleration, but, as has been customary in astrometry, the influence of the finite light-travel time is ignored.

Rigorous inclusion of the light-time effects results in a modification of the second and higher-order terms of the position as function of time. For the reduction of Hipparcos observations, where the propagation is only made over a few years, these differences can safely be ignored. However, it is not obvious that the effects are still negligible if the Hipparcos results are to be propagated over very long time intervals, say a hundred years or more. In fact, it would be desirable to have access to the rigorous formulae, for instance in the CD-ROM software, if only to remove any doubt as to its general applicability.

Closely linked with this problem is the propagation of the covariance of the astrometric parameters: to my knowledge, this has not before been considered in the context of the perspective changes.

2. Rigorous treatment of light-time effects

Perhaps the most complete treatment of the subject is given by Stumpff (A&A 144, 232, 1985). This reference contains a complete prescription for the rigorous propagation of barycentric stellar positions and proper motions in special relativity. In addition to the references quoted by Stumpff a short paper by Eisner (AJ 72, 214, 1967) should be mentioned as apparently the first modern discussion of the light-time effects. Murray's *Vectorial Astrometry* (1983), Sect. 2.6.4, provides a concise derivation of the classical perspective formula in a rigorous framework; however, the apparent acceleration due to the light-time effects is explicitly ignored (see below).

Stumpff's prescription for the rigorous propagation includes several factors depending on the ratio v/c , where v is the total barycentric velocity of the star and c the speed of light. Observationally, v must be obtained by combining the (spectroscopic) radial velocity and the tangential velocity, the latter basically given by μ/ϖ , where μ is the total proper motion and ϖ the parallax. For nearby stars with well-determined parameters, including radial velocities,

this treatment presents no practical problem and the modifications required with respect to a classical treatment are relatively simple.

For the majority of Hipparcos stars, however, the radial velocity is not known. This is not a serious problem, as the formula still makes sense if the radial velocity is *assumed* to be zero (at the catalogue epoch). More serious is that μ and ϖ are observational quantities subject to errors, and that μ/ϖ is therefore often an unreliable, or even senseless, estimate of the tangential velocity. Direct application of the rigorous formula in such cases may lead to unreasonable results or computational difficulties.

It appears, therefore, that the rigorous approach must be limited to nearby stars with well-determined astrometric data and known radial velocities, while some different approach must be adopted for the remaining stars. (A possible alternative would be to include spectrophotometric data and a kinematical model to obtain physically realistic estimates of the distances and space motions; but this appears much too complicated in relation to what could possibly be gained, and undesirable for other reasons.)

Alternatively we might seek some semi-rigorous treatment that can be formally applied to all stars, but which is still accurate enough for nearby stars. Hence the question: What is the highest-order approximation to the rigorous treatment that can sensibly be applied to any set of observed astrometric parameters (even $\varpi \leq 0$)?

3. Taylor expansion of the space motion

In the following I essentially adopt the notation used by Murray (VA, Chapter 2). Thus, t is the coordinate time for the event of light emission by the star and $\tilde{t}$ the coordinate time for light reception at the solar system barycentre. $\mathbf{b}$ is the barycentric coordinate vector to the star and $b = |\mathbf{b}|$ the barycentric distance. Because the light-travel time, $\tilde{t} - t = b/c$, is not accurately known for events outside the solar system, it is a practical necessity that all observables are referred to the barycentric time $\tilde{t}$.

The light-time effects arise from the circumstance that the 'apparent' space motion of the star, $\mathbf{b}(\tilde{t})$, is non-uniform, even though the true motion is assumed to be unaccelerated: $d^2\mathbf{b}/dt^2 = \mathbf{0}$. The effects are here studied by means of a Taylor expansion of $\mathbf{b}(\tilde{t})$ around the (barycentric) catalogue epoch $\tilde{T} = \text{J1991.25}$.

The observable quantities are the barycentric unit vector towards the star $\mathbf{u}$, the parallax ϖ (actually the sine of the parallax), the proper motion μ , and the radial velocity¹ ρ :

¹As defined by Eq. (4) ρ is, strictly speaking, not directly observable by purely spectroscopic means. In terms of the Doppler displacement $z = (\lambda_{\text{obs}} - \lambda_{\text{lab}})/\lambda_{\text{lab}}$, which we may assume has already been corrected for the moving observer and possible convective motions of the stellar atmosphere, we have (VA, Eq. 2.6.24):

$$\rho = c(1+z)^{-1} \left(z - \frac{\Phi}{c^2} - \frac{v^2}{2c^2} \right).$$

Φ is the gravitational potential at the star's surface, v the total barycentric velocity. The term $-\Phi c^{-2}$ thus corrects for the gravitational redshift while $-v^2/(2c^2)$ arises from the Lorentz factor on the proper time at the moving source. In principle, therefore, the true space velocity is needed already for a rigorous interpretation of the Doppler effect. Although Stumpff does take into account the Lorentz factor by an iterative procedure, I will ignore this complication simply by considering ρ as an observable. Thus, either ρ is taken to be known (to a certain accuracy), in which case I assume that the relevant corrections have been applied, or, in the absence of other information, $\rho = 0$ is adopted.

$$\mathbf{u} = \langle \mathbf{b} \rangle \equiv \mathbf{b} b^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

$$\varpi = a_u b^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{d\tilde{t}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\rho = \frac{db}{d\tilde{t}}. \quad (4)$$

a_u is the astronomical unit. In principle these observables give directly the barycentric position

$$\mathbf{b} = \langle \mathbf{b} \rangle b = \mathbf{u} a_u / \varpi \quad (5)$$

and the barycentric rate of change of the position,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} = \langle \mathbf{b} \rangle \frac{db}{d\tilde{t}} + \frac{d\langle \mathbf{b} \rangle}{d\tilde{t}} b \quad (6)$$

$$= \mathbf{u} \rho + \mu a_u / \varpi. \quad (7)$$

In order to obtain the higher derivatives of $\mathbf{b}$ with respect to $\tilde{t}$ it is necessary to introduce explicitly the assumption of uniform space motion. From $b = c(\tilde{t} - t)$ we have $\rho = c(1 - dt/d\tilde{t})$ or

$$\frac{dt}{d\tilde{t}} = 1 - \frac{\rho}{c}. \quad (8)$$

Writing

$$\frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} = \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{dt} \frac{dt}{d\tilde{t}} = \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{dt} \left(1 - \frac{\rho}{c}\right) \quad (9)$$

we find, if db/dt is constant,

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}^2} = - \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{dt} \frac{d\rho}{d\tilde{t}} \frac{1}{c} = - \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} \frac{d\rho}{d\tilde{t}} \frac{1}{c - \rho}. \quad (10)$$

From $\rho = \mathbf{u}'(d\mathbf{b}/d\tilde{t})$ we have

$$\frac{d\rho}{d\tilde{t}} = \mu' \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} + \mathbf{u}' \frac{d^2\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}^2}. \quad (11)$$

By means of Eqs. (6) and (10) we now find

$$\frac{d\rho}{d\tilde{t}} = \mu^2 (a_u / \varpi) (1 - \rho/c) \quad (12)$$

and

$$\frac{d^2\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}^2} = - \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} \frac{\mu^2 a_u}{c\varpi}. \quad (13)$$

By differentiation of Eq. (6) we also find the rate of change of the proper motion,

$$\frac{d\mu}{d\tilde{t}} = -\mathbf{u} \mu^2 - \mu \left(\frac{2\rho\varpi}{a_u} + \frac{\mu^2 a_u}{c\varpi} \right). \quad (14)$$

Higher derivatives of $\mathbf{b}(\tilde{t})$ can be obtained by straightforward differentiation of Eq. (13). For the third derivative I find:

$$\frac{d^3\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}^3} = \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} \left[3\mu^2 \rho + 3 \left(\frac{\mu^2 a_u}{c\varpi} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (15)$$

Murray (1983), for his Eq. (2.6.25) and following, explicitly assumes $|d^2\mathbf{b}/d\tilde{t}^2| = 0$ and consequently does not find the light-time terms (containing c) in the derivatives of ρ and μ . It is not clear from the text if this is an oversight or an expedient approximation.

To second order in $\tilde{t}$ the Taylor expansion of the barycentric motion becomes:

$$\mathbf{b}(\tilde{t}) \simeq \mathbf{b}(\tilde{T}) + \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}}(\tilde{t} - \tilde{T}) + \frac{d^2\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}^2} \frac{1}{2}(\tilde{t} - \tilde{T})^2 \quad (16)$$

$$= \mathbf{u} a_u/\varpi + (\mathbf{u}\rho + \mu a_u/\varpi)(\tilde{t} - \tilde{T}) \left[1 - \frac{\mu^2 a_u}{2c\varpi}(\tilde{t} - \tilde{T}) \right], \quad (17)$$

where the observables on the right-hand side all refer to the epoch $\tilde{T}$.

The size of the ‘apparent acceleration’ can be written as $|d^2\mathbf{b}/d\tilde{t}^2| = vv_t^2/cb$, where $v_t = \mu b$ is the tangential velocity. For Barnard’s Star ($\mu = 10.3$ arcsec yr $^{-1}$, $\rho = -108$ km s $^{-1}$, $\varpi = 0.545$ arcsec) we have $v = 140$ km s $^{-1}$, $v_t = 90$ km s $^{-1}$ and $b = 5.7 \cdot 10^{13}$ km, and consequently

$$\left| \frac{d^2\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}^2} \right| \simeq 7 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ km s}^{-2}. \quad (18)$$

It is not likely that this value is exceeded by any other star in the Hipparcos programme. It is instructive to compare it with the true acceleration of a star in a circular galactic orbit at the Sun’s distance from the Galactic Centre, $(250 \text{ km s}^{-1})^2/(8 \text{ kpc}) \simeq 2.5 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ km s}^{-2}$. The conclusion is that $|d^2\mathbf{b}/d\tilde{t}^2| = 0$, as assumed by Murray, is an acceptable approximation at the precision level where we neglect the curvature of the galactic orbits.

While light-time effects are thus negligible for the *propagation* of the astrometric parameters, they should still be kept in mind for the *kinematical interpretation* of the observables. For instance, from Eqs. (7) and (9) we obtain the following expression for the space velocity:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{b}}{d\tilde{t}} = (\mathbf{u}\rho + \mu a_u/\varpi)(1 - \rho/c)^{-1}. \quad (19)$$

This differs from the classical formula by the Doppler factor $(1 - \rho/c)^{-1}$.

4. The barycentric direction as function of time

Multiplying Eq. (16) by ϖ/a_u and normalizing the resulting vector (which is already very close to unit length) results in the following expression for the barycentric direction as function of barycentric time:

$$\mathbf{u}(\tilde{t}) = \left\langle \mathbf{u} \left[1 + \frac{\rho\varpi}{a_u} \tilde{\tau} - \frac{\mu^2 \rho}{2c} \tilde{\tau}^2 + O(\tilde{\tau}^3) \right] + \mu \left[\tilde{\tau} - \frac{\mu^2 a_u}{2c\varpi} \tilde{\tau}^2 + O(\tilde{\tau}^3) \right] \right\rangle \quad (20)$$

where $\tilde{\tau} = \tilde{t} - \tilde{T}$. Again it should be noted that, on the right-hand side, $\mathbf{u}$, ϖ , μ and ρ all refer to the catalogue epoch $\tilde{T}$.

With present notations the relevant part of the formula used in the NDAC data reductions (A&A 258, 18, 1992; Eq. A.1) reads

$$\mathbf{u}(\tilde{t}) = \langle \mathbf{u} [1 + (\rho\varpi/a_u) \tilde{\tau}] + \mu \tilde{\tau} \rangle. \quad (21)$$

To the first order in $\tilde{\tau}$ this is identical to the rigorous expression. The higher-order terms in Eq. (20) all contain the factor c^{-1} and are thus attributable to the light-time effects.

Considering the second-order terms in Eq. (20) we see that the radial term, $-(\mu^2 \rho / 2c) \tilde{\tau}^2$, could be applied to all stars without any practical or computational problem. The tangential term, on the other hand, contains the parallax in the denominator and therefore cannot be indiscriminately applied. In practice the tangential term is usually the more important one, because the radial term only causes an indirect effect on the position due to the proper motion. Again we may take Barnard's Star as an extreme example: the effect of the radial term on the position is approximately $|\mu (\mu^2 \rho / 2c) \tilde{\tau}^3| \simeq 4.6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ mas yr}^{-3}$, while the tangential term is $|\mu (\mu^2 a_u / 2c \varpi) \tilde{\tau}^2| \simeq 7.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mas yr}^{-2}$. The light-time effects thus remain below 1 mas over a time span of 100 yr.

In conclusion, it appears that (i) the first-order formula, Eq. (21), is the highest-order propagation formula that can safely be used with any set of observed parameters, and (ii) the effect of the second-order terms is, even for Barnard's Star, less than 1 mas over a century. Consequently I adopt the semi-rigorous formula, Eq. (21), as the basis for all subsequent development.

5. Propagation of the six astrometric parameters

In the following I shall use subscript $_0$ to denote values at the catalogue epoch $\tilde{T}$, while unsubscripted variables are considered to be functions of $\tilde{t} = \tilde{T} + \tilde{\tau}$. In the framework of the adopted propagation model, Eq. (21), it is convenient to introduce $\zeta = \rho \varpi / a_u$ as the sixth astrometric parameter, after α , δ , ϖ , $\mu_\alpha^* = \mu_\alpha \cos \delta$ and μ_δ . ζ is dimensionally equivalent to the proper motion and statistically of a similar size; it is therefore conveniently measured in $[\text{mas yr}^{-1}]$.² Introducing also the distance factor

$$f = b_0/b = [1 + 2\zeta_0 \tilde{\tau} + (\mu_0^2 + \zeta_0^2) \tilde{\tau}^2]^{-1/2} \quad (22)$$

we can write Eq. (21)

$$\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}_0(1 + \zeta_0 \tilde{\tau}) + \mu_0 \tilde{\tau}] f, \quad (23)$$

and the propagation of the parallax becomes

$$\varpi = \varpi_0 f. \quad (24)$$

Direct differentiation of Eq. (22) gives:

$$\frac{df}{d\tilde{t}} = -[\zeta_0 + (\mu_0^2 + \zeta_0^2) \tilde{\tau}] f^3 \quad (25)$$

and hence

$$\mu = \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{d\tilde{t}} = [\mu_0(1 + \zeta_0 \tilde{\tau}) - \mathbf{u}_0 \mu_0^2 \tilde{\tau}] f^3. \quad (26)$$

Finally,

$$\zeta = \frac{db}{d\tilde{t}} \frac{\varpi}{a_u} = [\zeta_0 + (\mu_0^2 + \zeta_0^2) \tilde{\tau}] f^2. \quad (27)$$

These equations give the exact propagation of the six astrometric parameters within the adopted (semi-rigorous) model.

²If ρ is measured in $[\text{km s}^{-1}]$, ϖ in $[\text{mas}]$ and ζ in $[\text{mas yr}^{-1}]$, then $\zeta = \rho \varpi / 4.7404705$.

6. Propagation of covariance

Let C_0 be the 6×6 covariance matrix of the astrometric parameters $\mathbf{a}_0$ referring to epoch $\tilde{T}$. After propagation to epoch $\tilde{t}$ the covariance becomes

$$C = D C_0 D' \quad (28)$$

where D is the matrix of partial derivatives, $\{D\}_{ij} = \partial\{a\}_i / \partial\{a_0\}_j$.

The calculation of the partial derivatives requires some additional comments on the exact definition of the parameter vector $\mathbf{a}$. At first sight, the natural definition would be to regard the numerical quantities α , δ , ϖ , μ_α^* , μ_δ and ζ as the components of $\mathbf{a}$. However, it turns out that this choice introduces certain formal correlations among the propagated parameters, which would probably be perceived as unnatural by most users. This is related to the circumstance that the proper motion components are measured along axes whose directions depend on the position of the star; consequently, their numerical values depend on the values of α and δ , even if the proper motion vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is considered to be independent of the position vector $\mathbf{u}$.

Formally, the situation can be described as follows. The relation between $\mathbf{u}$ and the barycentric right ascension and declination is given by

$$\mathbf{u} = N \begin{bmatrix} \cos \delta \cos \alpha \\ \cos \delta \sin \alpha \\ \sin \delta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (29)$$

where $N = [l \ m \ n]$ is the equatorial triad. Following Murray, we also define the 'normal triad' $\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{p} \ \mathbf{q} \ \mathbf{r}]$ at $\mathbf{u}$, relative to N , by means of

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{u}, \quad \mathbf{p} = \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{r} \rangle, \quad \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{p}. \quad (30)$$

$\mathbf{p}$ and $\mathbf{q}$ are unit vectors in the directions of increasing α and δ , respectively; they are therefore the axes along which the proper motion components are measured:

$$\mu_\alpha^* = \mathbf{p}' \boldsymbol{\mu}, \quad \mu_\delta = \mathbf{q}' \boldsymbol{\mu}. \quad (31)$$

The question is whether $\mathbf{R}$ should be regarded as a fixed frame, or if its dependence on $\mathbf{u}$ according to Eq. (30) (and hence on α , δ) explicitly should be taken into account in computing the partial derivatives. I advocate the former solution as being closer to our intuitive understanding of the uncertainties. It is also consistent with the definition of the proper motion components as the coordinates of $d\mathbf{u}/d\tilde{t}$ in the *fixed* frame $\mathbf{R}$.

Having made this choice the distinction between $\mathbf{u}$ and $\mathbf{r}$ becomes essential for the development of the partial derivatives, although the two vectors coincide at the *nominal* position of the star. Thus we must write

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{p}\xi + \mathbf{q}\eta + \mathbf{r}(1 - \xi^2 - \eta^2)^{1/2}, \quad (32)$$

where ξ and η are the variations of $\mathbf{u}$ in the two tangential directions; $\xi = \eta = 0$ corresponds to the nominal position. Taking the time derivative, and defining $\mu_\alpha^* = d\xi/d\tilde{t}$ and $\mu_\delta = d\eta/d\tilde{t}$, we have

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \mathbf{p}\mu_\alpha^* + \mathbf{q}\mu_\delta - \mathbf{r}(\xi\mu_\alpha^* + \eta\mu_\delta)(1 - \xi^2 - \eta^2)^{-1/2}. \quad (33)$$

The initial parameter vector can now be formally identified as $\mathbf{a}_0 = [\xi_0 \ \eta_0 \ \varpi_0 \ \mu_{\alpha 0}^* \ \mu_{\delta 0} \ \zeta_0]'$ relative to the fixed initial normal triad $\mathbf{R}_0$ at $\mathbf{u}_0$; similarly the propagated parameter vector

is given by $\mathbf{a} = [\xi \ \eta \ \varpi \ \mu_\alpha^* \ \mu_\delta \ \zeta]'$ relative to the fixed normal triad $\mathbf{R}$ at $\mathbf{u}$. The partial derivatives are calculated by means of the above expressions and evaluated at the nominal positions, $\xi_0 = \eta_0 = 0$ and $\xi = \eta = 0$. This calculation is straightforward, if somewhat tedious, and the results are given below without further comment.

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{11} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \xi_0} = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{p}_0(1 + \zeta_0\tilde{\tau})f - \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{r}_0\mu_{\alpha 0}^*\tilde{\tau}f \quad (34)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{12} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \eta_0} = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{q}_0(1 + \zeta_0\tilde{\tau})f - \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{r}_0\mu_{\delta 0}\tilde{\tau}f \quad (35)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{13} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \varpi_0} = 0 \quad (36)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{14} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mu_{\alpha 0}^*} = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{p}_0\tilde{\tau}f \quad (37)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{15} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \mu_{\delta 0}} = \mathbf{p}'\mathbf{q}_0\tilde{\tau}f \quad (38)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{16} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \zeta_0} = -\mu_\alpha^*\tilde{\tau}^2 \quad (39)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{21} = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \xi_0} = \mathbf{q}'\mathbf{p}_0(1 + \zeta_0\tilde{\tau})f - \mathbf{q}'\mathbf{r}_0\mu_{\alpha 0}^*\tilde{\tau}f \quad (40)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{22} = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \eta_0} = \mathbf{q}'\mathbf{q}_0(1 + \zeta_0\tilde{\tau})f - \mathbf{q}'\mathbf{r}_0\mu_{\delta 0}\tilde{\tau}f \quad (41)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{23} = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \varpi_0} = 0 \quad (42)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{24} = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \mu_{\alpha 0}^*} = \mathbf{q}'\mathbf{p}_0\tilde{\tau}f \quad (43)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{25} = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \mu_{\delta 0}} = \mathbf{q}'\mathbf{q}_0\tilde{\tau}f \quad (44)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{26} = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial \zeta_0} = -\mu_\delta\tilde{\tau}^2 \quad (45)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{31} = \frac{\partial \varpi}{\partial \xi_0} = 0 \quad (46)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{32} = \frac{\partial \varpi}{\partial \eta_0} = 0 \quad (47)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{33} = \frac{\partial \varpi}{\partial \varpi_0} = f \quad (48)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{34} = \frac{\partial \varpi}{\partial \mu_{\alpha 0}^*} = -\varpi\mu_{\alpha 0}^*\tilde{\tau}^2f^2 \quad (49)$$

$$\{\mathbf{D}\}_{35} = \frac{\partial \varpi}{\partial \mu_{\delta 0}} = -\varpi\mu_{\delta 0}\tilde{\tau}^2f^2 \quad (50)$$

$$\{D\}_{36} = \frac{\partial \varpi}{\partial \zeta_0} = -\varpi(1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) \bar{\tau} f^2 \quad (51)$$

$$\{D\}_{41} = \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha^*}{\partial \xi_0} = -\mathbf{p}' \mathbf{p}_0 \mu_0^2 \bar{\tau} f^3 - \mathbf{p}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\alpha 0}^* (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 \quad (52)$$

$$\{D\}_{42} = \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha^*}{\partial \eta_0} = -\mathbf{p}' \mathbf{q}_0 \mu_0^2 \bar{\tau} f^3 - \mathbf{p}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\delta 0} (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 \quad (53)$$

$$\{D\}_{43} = \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha^*}{\partial \varpi_0} = 0 \quad (54)$$

$$\{D\}_{44} = \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha^*}{\partial \mu_{\alpha 0}^*} = \mathbf{p}' \mathbf{p}_0 (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 - 2\mathbf{p}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\alpha 0}^* \bar{\tau} f^3 - 3\mu_\alpha^* \mu_{\alpha 0}^* \bar{\tau}^2 f^2 \quad (55)$$

$$\{D\}_{45} = \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha^*}{\partial \mu_{\delta 0}} = \mathbf{p}' \mathbf{q}_0 (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 - 2\mathbf{p}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\delta 0} \bar{\tau} f^3 - 3\mu_\alpha^* \mu_{\delta 0} \bar{\tau}^2 f^2 \quad (56)$$

$$\{D\}_{46} = \frac{\partial \mu_\alpha^*}{\partial \zeta_0} = \mathbf{p}' [\mu_0 f - 3\mu(1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau})] \bar{\tau} f^2 \quad (57)$$

$$\{D\}_{51} = \frac{\partial \mu_\delta}{\partial \xi_0} = -\mathbf{q}' \mathbf{p}_0 \mu_0^2 \bar{\tau} f^3 - \mathbf{q}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\alpha 0}^* (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 \quad (58)$$

$$\{D\}_{52} = \frac{\partial \mu_\delta}{\partial \eta_0} = -\mathbf{q}' \mathbf{q}_0 \mu_0^2 \bar{\tau} f^3 - \mathbf{q}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\delta 0} (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 \quad (59)$$

$$\{D\}_{53} = \frac{\partial \mu_\delta}{\partial \varpi_0} = 0 \quad (60)$$

$$\{D\}_{54} = \frac{\partial \mu_\delta}{\partial \mu_{\alpha 0}^*} = \mathbf{q}' \mathbf{p}_0 (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 - 2\mathbf{q}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\alpha 0}^* \bar{\tau} f^3 - 3\mu_\delta \mu_{\alpha 0}^* \bar{\tau}^2 f^2 \quad (61)$$

$$\{D\}_{55} = \frac{\partial \mu_\delta}{\partial \mu_{\delta 0}} = \mathbf{q}' \mathbf{q}_0 (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) f^3 - 2\mathbf{q}' \mathbf{r}_0 \mu_{\delta 0} \bar{\tau} f^3 - 3\mu_\delta \mu_{\delta 0} \bar{\tau}^2 f^2 \quad (62)$$

$$\{D\}_{56} = \frac{\partial \mu_\delta}{\partial \zeta_0} = \mathbf{q}' [\mu_0 f - 3\mu(1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau})] \bar{\tau} f^2 \quad (63)$$

$$\{D\}_{61} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \xi_0} = 0 \quad (64)$$

$$\{D\}_{62} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \eta_0} = 0 \quad (65)$$

$$\{D\}_{63} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \varpi_0} = 0 \quad (66)$$

$$\{D\}_{64} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mu_{\alpha 0}^*} = 2\mu_{\alpha 0}^* (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) \bar{\tau} f^4 \quad (67)$$

$$\{D\}_{65} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mu_{\delta 0}} = 2\mu_{\delta 0} (1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau}) \bar{\tau} f^4 \quad (68)$$

$$\{D\}_{66} = \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \zeta_0} = [(1 + \zeta_0 \bar{\tau})^2 - \mu_0^2 \bar{\tau}^2] f^4 \quad (69)$$

7. FORTRAN implementation

The following subroutine performs the transformation of a vector of astrometric parameters $\mathbf{a}$, and its associated covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}$, from one epoch to another. The positional components in $\mathbf{a}$ are α and δ expressed in [deg], although the corresponding elements of the covariance matrix refer to ξ and η , expressed in [mas] relative to the fixed normal triad at the position.

```
*****
      SUBROUTINE prop6(t0, a0, c0, t, a, c)
*****
c
c Propagates the 6-dimensional vector of astrometric parameters
c and the associated covariance matrix from barycentric epoch
c t0 to t
c
c
c INPUT (all real variables are DOUBLE PRECISION):
c
c t0      = original epoch [yr] - see Note 1
c a0(1)   = right ascension at t0 [deg]
c a0(2)   = declination at t0 [deg]
c a0(3)   = parallax at t0 [mas]
c a0(4)   = proper motion in R.A., mult by cos(Dec), at t0 [mas/yr]
c a0(5)   = proper motion in Dec at t0 [mas/yr]
c a0(6)   = normalised radial velocity at t0 [mas/yr] - see Note 2
c c0(i,j) = cov[a0(i),a0(j)] in [mas^2, mas^2/yr, mas^2/yr^2]
c t       = new epoch [yr] - see Note 1
c
c
c OUTPUT (all real variables are DOUBLE PRECISION):
c
c a(1)    = right ascension at t [deg]
c a(2)    = declination at t [deg]
c a(3)    = parallax at t [mas]
c a(4)    = proper motion in R.A., mult by cos(Dec), at t [mas/yr]
c a(5)    = proper motion in Dec at t [mas/yr]
c a(6)    = normalised radial velocity at t [mas/yr]
c c(i,j)  = cov[a(i),a(j)] in [mas^2, mas^2/yr, mas^2/yr^2]
c
c
c FUNCTIONS/SUBROUTINES CALLED:
c
c DP FUNCTION scalar = scalar product of two vectors
c
c
c NOTES:
c
c 1. Only t-t0 is used; the origin of the time scale is
c    therefore irrelevant but must be the same for t0 and t.
c 2. The normalised radial velocity at epoch t0 is given by
c    a0(6) = vr0*a0(3)/4.7404705
c    where vr0 is the barycentric radial velocity in [km/s] at
c    epoch t0; similarly a(6) = vr*a(3)/4.7404704 at epoch t.
c 3. This routine adheres to ANSI Fortran 77, except for the use
c    of lower-case letters. All variables are declared.
c
c
c WRITTEN BY:
```

```

c
c L Lindegren, Lund Observatory, 15 March 1995
c
c-----
c Input/output variables:
c-----
      DOUBLE PRECISION t0, a0(6), c0(6,6), t, a(6), c(6,6)
c-----
c Function called:
c-----
      DOUBLE PRECISION scalar
c-----
c Constants:
c-----
      DOUBLE PRECISION zero, one, two, three
      PARAMETER (zero = 0d0, one = 1d0, two = 2d0, three = 3d0)
      DOUBLE PRECISION pi, rdpdeg, rdpmas, eps
      PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265358979324d0)
      PARAMETER (rdpdeg = (pi/180d0))
      PARAMETER (rdpmas = (pi/(180d0*3600d3)))
      PARAMETER (eps = 1d-9)
c-----
c Auxiliary variables:
c-----
      INTEGER i, j, k, l
      DOUBLE PRECISION tau, alpha0, delta0, par0, pma0, pmd0, zeta0,
1   ca0, sa0, cd0, sd0, xy, alpha, delta, par, pma, pmd, zeta,
2   w, f, f2, f3, f4, tau2, pm02, pp0, pq0, pr0, qp0, qq0, qr0,
3   ppmz, qpmz, sum, r0(3), p0(3), q0(3), pmv0(3), d(6,6),
4   pmv(3), p(3), q(3), r(3), pmz(3)
c-----
c Convert input data to internal units (rad, year):
c-----
      tau   = t - t0
      alpha0 = a0(1)*rdpdeg
      delta0 = a0(2)*rdpdeg
      par0   = a0(3)*rdpmas
      pma0   = a0(4)*rdpmas
      pmd0   = a0(5)*rdpmas
      zeta0  = a0(6)*rdpmas
c-----
c Calculate normal triad [p0 q0 r0] at t0; r0 is
c also the unit vector to the star at epoch t0:
c-----
      ca0 = dcos(alpha0)
      sa0 = dsin(alpha0)
      cd0 = dcos(delta0)
      sd0 = dsin(delta0)
c
      p0(1) = -sa0
      p0(2) = ca0
      p0(3) = zero
c
      q0(1) = -sd0*ca0
      q0(2) = -sd0*sa0
      q0(3) = cd0
c
      r0(1) = cd0*ca0
      r0(2) = cd0*sa0
      r0(3) = sd0
c-----
c Proper motion vector:

```

```

c-----
      pmv0(1) = p0(1)*pma0 + q0(1)*pmd0
      pmv0(2) = p0(2)*pma0 + q0(2)*pmd0
      pmv0(3) = p0(3)*pma0 + q0(3)*pmd0
c-----
c  Various auxiliary quantities:
c-----
      tau2 = tau**2
      pm02 = pma0**2 + pmd0**2
      w = one + zeta0*tau
      f2 = one/(one + two*zeta0*tau + (pm02 + zeta0**2)*tau2)
      f = dsqrt(f2)
      f3 = f2*f
      f4 = f2**2
c-----
c  The position vector and parallax at t:
c-----
      r(1) = (r0(1)*w + pmv0(1)*tau)*f
      r(2) = (r0(2)*w + pmv0(2)*tau)*f
      r(3) = (r0(3)*w + pmv0(3)*tau)*f
c
      par = par0*f
c-----
c  The proper motion vector and normalised radial velocity at t:
c-----
      pmv(1) = (pmv0(1)*w - r0(1)*pm02*tau)*f3
      pmv(2) = (pmv0(2)*w - r0(2)*pm02*tau)*f3
      pmv(3) = (pmv0(3)*w - r0(3)*pm02*tau)*f3
c
      zeta = (zeta0 + (pm02 + zeta0**2)*tau)*f2
c-----
c  The normal triad [p q r] at t; if r is very
c  close to the pole, select p towards RA=90 deg:
c-----
      xy = dsqrt(r(1)**2 + r(2)**2)
      IF (xy .LT. eps) THEN
        p(1) = zero
        p(2) = one
        p(3) = zero
      ELSE
        p(1) = -r(2)/xy
        p(2) = r(1)/xy
        p(3) = zero
      ENDIF
c
      q(1) = r(2)*p(3) - r(3)*p(2)
      q(2) = r(3)*p(1) - r(1)*p(3)
      q(3) = r(1)*p(2) - r(2)*p(1)
c-----
c  Convert parameters at t to external units:
c-----
      alpha = datan2(-p(1), p(2))
      IF (alpha .LT. zero) alpha = alpha + two*pi
      delta = datan2(r(3), xy)
      pma = scalar(p, pmv)
      pmd = scalar(q, pmv)
c
      a(1) = alpha/rdpdeg
      a(2) = delta/rdpdeg
      a(3) = par/rdpmas
      a(4) = pma/rdpmas
      a(5) = pmd/rdpmas

```

```

a(6) = zeta/rdpmas
-----
c Auxiliary quantities for the partial derivatives:
-----
pmz(1) = pmv0(1)*f - three*pmv(1)*w
pmz(2) = pmv0(2)*f - three*pmv(2)*w
pmz(3) = pmv0(3)*f - three*pmv(3)*w
c
pp0 = scalar(p, p0)
pq0 = scalar(p, q0)
pr0 = scalar(p, r0)
qp0 = scalar(q, p0)
qq0 = scalar(q, q0)
qr0 = scalar(q, r0)
ppmz = scalar(p, pmz)
qpmz = scalar(q, pmz)
-----
c Partial derivatives:
-----
d(1,1) = pp0*w*f - pr0*pma0*tau*f
d(1,2) = pq0*w*f - pr0*pmd0*tau*f
d(1,3) = zero
d(1,4) = pp0*tau*f
d(1,5) = pq0*tau*f
d(1,6) = -pma*tau2
c
d(2,1) = qp0*w*f - qr0*pma0*tau*f
d(2,2) = qq0*w*f - qr0*pmd0*tau*f
d(2,3) = zero
d(2,4) = qp0*tau*f
d(2,5) = qq0*tau*f
d(2,6) = -pmd*tau2
c
d(3,1) = zero
d(3,2) = zero
d(3,3) = f
d(3,4) = -par*pma0*tau2*f2
d(3,5) = -par*pmd0*tau2*f2
d(3,6) = -par*w*tau*f2
c
d(4,1) = -pp0*pm02*tau*f3 - pr0*pma0*w*f3
d(4,2) = -pq0*pm02*tau*f3 - pr0*pmd0*w*f3
d(4,3) = zero
d(4,4) = pp0*w*f3 - two*pr0*pma0*tau*f3 - three*pma*pma0*tau2*f2
d(4,5) = pq0*w*f3 - two*pr0*pmd0*tau*f3 - three*pma*pmd0*tau2*f2
d(4,6) = ppmz*tau*f2
c
d(5,1) = -qp0*pm02*tau*f3 - qr0*pma0*w*f3
d(5,2) = -qq0*pm02*tau*f3 - qr0*pmd0*w*f3
d(5,3) = zero
d(5,4) = qp0*w*f3 - two*qr0*pma0*tau*f3 - three*pmd*pma0*tau2*f2
d(5,5) = qq0*w*f3 - two*qr0*pmd0*tau*f3 - three*pmd*pmd0*tau2*f2
d(5,6) = qpmz*tau*f2
c
d(6,1) = zero
d(6,2) = zero
d(6,3) = zero
d(6,4) = two*pma0*w*tau*f4
d(6,5) = two*pmd0*w*tau*f4
d(6,6) = (w**2 - pm02*tau2)*f4
-----
c Propagate the covariance as c = d*c0*d':

```

```

-----
      DO 140 i = 1, 6
        DO 130 j = 1, 6
          sum = zero
          DO 120 k = 1, 6
            DO 110 l = 1, 6
              sum = sum + d(i,k)*c0(k,l)*d(j,l)
110          CONTINUE
120          CONTINUE
            c(i,j) = sum
130        CONTINUE
140      CONTINUE
c
      RETURN
      END
c*****
      DOUBLE PRECISION FUNCTION scalar(x, y)
c*****
c
c  Scalar product of x(1:3) and y(1:3)
c
      DOUBLE PRECISION x(3), y(3)
      scalar = x(1)*y(1) + x(2)*y(2) + x(3)*y(3)
      RETURN
      END

```

8. Numerical example

The Fortran program below propagates the astrometric parameters, and an associated covariance matrix, 10 000 years forward and backward in time, using the subroutine in Section 7. The parameters at the original epoch (2000.0) are approximately those of Barnard's star, as taken from HIC, but with the position rounded to the nearest degree. The covariances at the original epoch correspond to uncorrelated parameters with standard errors of 1 mas and 1 mas yr⁻¹; however, for the radial velocity a standard error of 0.5 km s⁻¹ is taken, and the radial velocity is assumed to be uncorrelated with the parallax. Note that there is then a negative correlation between ϖ and ζ .

The output from the program is listed after the code. The original parameters and covariances are recovered to within the precision of the printout.

```

c*****
PROGRAM prpcov
c*****
c
c Test program for subroutine prop6
c
c Propagates the approximate astrometric parameters of Barnard's star
c (HIC 87937) 10000 years forward in time, then back to original epoch
c
DOUBLE PRECISION t0, a0(6), c0(6,6), t, a(6), c(6,6),
1 const, vr0, sevr0, vr, sevr
INTEGER i, j
c
DATA c0/36*0d0/, const/4.7404705d0/
vr0 = -106.800d0
sevr0 = 0.5d0
t0 = 2000.000d0
a0(1) = 269.000d0
a0(2) = +5.000d0
a0(3) = 545.000d0
a0(4) = -803.000d0
a0(5) = 10278.000d0
a0(6) = vr0*a0(3)/const
c0(1,1) = 1d0**2
c0(2,2) = 1d0**2
c0(3,3) = 1d0**2
c0(4,4) = 1d0**2
c0(5,5) = 1d0**2
c0(6,6) = ((a0(3)*sevr0)**2 + c0(3,3)*vr0**2)/const**2
c0(3,6) = vr0*c0(3,3)/const
c0(6,3) = vr0*c0(3,3)/const
t = 12000.000d0
c
WRITE(*, '/a,f8.1/(f15.8,6f17.3)')
1 'Original parameters and covariances at epoch =', t0,
2 (a0(i), (c0(i,j), j=1,6), i=1,6)
WRITE(*, '(a,f9.4,a,f6.4,a)')
1 '(Radial velocity = ', vr0, ' km/s; se = ', sevr0, ' km/s)'
c-----
CALL prop6(t0, a0, c0, t, a, c)
c-----
vr = const*a(6)/a(3)
sevr = (const/a(3))*dsqrt(c(6,6) + (a(6)/a(3))**2*c(3,3)
1 - 2d0*(a(6)/a(3))*c(3,6))
WRITE(*, '/a,f8.1/(f15.8,6f17.3)')
1 'Propagated parameters and covariances at epoch =', t,
2 (a(i), (c(i,j), j=1,6), i=1,6)
WRITE(*, '(a,f9.4,a,f6.4,a)')
1 '(Radial velocity = ', vr, ' km/s; se = ', sevr, ' km/s)'
c-----
CALL prop6(t, a, c, t0, a0, c0)
c-----
vr0 = const*a0(6)/a0(3)
sevr0 = (const/a0(3))*dsqrt(c0(6,6) + (a0(6)/a0(3))**2*c0(3,3)
1 - 2d0*(a0(6)/a0(3))*c0(3,6))
WRITE(*, '/a,f8.1/(f15.8,6f17.3)')
1 'Back-propagated parameters and covariances at epoch =', t0,
2 (a0(i), (c0(i,j), j=1,6), i=1,6)
WRITE(*, '(a,f9.4,a,f6.4,a)')
1 '(Radial velocity = ', vr0, ' km/s; se = ', sevr0, ' km/s)'
c
END

```

Output from the above program (only the column widths have been edited):

Original parameters and covariances at epoch = 2000.0

269.00000000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
5.00000000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
545.00000000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
-803.00000000	.000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	-22.529	
10278.00000000	.000	.000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	
-12278.52804906	.000	.000	-22.529	.000	.000	1.000	.000	
(Radial velocity = -106.8000 km/s; se = .5000 km/s)							.000	3811.955

Propagated parameters and covariances at epoch = 12000.0

262.82375996	10825856627.158	-76013261313.480	-313700.592	2094984.893	-14875954.251	-3197197.489		
55.76098296	-76013261313.480	546157411699.941	2252949.760	-14875954.251	106860490.082	22961784.223		
847.42606613	-313700.592	2252949.760	11.398	-61.408	441.026	94.545		
-3437.43746151	2094984.893	-14875954.251	-61.408	407.745	-2911.738	-624.910		
24687.15102392	-14875954.251	106860490.082	441.026	-2911.738	20913.970	4488.006		
443.25359055	-3197197.489	22961784.223	94.545	-624.910	4488.006	969.209		
(Radial velocity = 2.4795 km/s; se = .1653 km/s)								

Back-propagated parameters and covariances at epoch = 2000.0

269.00000000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
5.00000000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
545.00000000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
-803.00000000	.000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	-22.529	
10278.00000000	.000	.000	.000	.000	1.000	.000	.000	
-12278.52804906	.000	.000	-22.529	.000	.000	1.000	.000	
(Radial velocity = -106.8000 km/s; se = .5000 km/s)							.000	3811.955